

Detection of Myocardial Infarction from Electrocardiogram

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ABSTRACT

Myocardial Infarction (MI) is a deadly disease that kills people of all ages. Prevention from heart disease complication can be done if MI is detected at an early stage. The purpose of this research is to improvise method in determining presence of MI based on the analysis of electrocardiogram (ECG) signal in a real time manner. ST segment elevation in ECG signal is set as an indicator to determine the presence of MI in ECG signal. Software MATLAB programming is used to extract the ECG features and ST deviation, and detection of MI. Process in determining MI starts with collection of ECG signal that can be obtained from free source website, Physionet, followed by ECG signal pre-processing to filter and corrects the baseline wandering. Next, ECG signal processing is done to extract the ECG features, which are peaks P, Q, R, S, and T. After that, Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) analysis is conducted in detecting any deviation in ST elevation spectrum and finally, an alert is displayed to warn the users if MI is detected in ECG signal. The correct window size for CUSUM analysis is investigated in this research to obtain the optimum sensitivity and specificity up to 90%. In general, use a long window for data that does not change rapidly, meanwhile use a smaller window for data that changes fast. By correct setting of window size and choosing efficient CUSUM analysis, MI can be detected at an early stage by analysis of ECG signal.

Keywords: Myocardial Infarction, Electrocardiogram, ST Elevation, Cumulative Sum, Window Size

ABSTRAK

Infarksi Miokardium (MI) merupakan penyakit pembunuh tanpa mengira usia. Pencegahan daripada komplikasi penyakit jantung dapat dilaksanakan sekiranya MI dikesan pada peringkat awal. Kajian ini dijalankan untuk menambah baik kaedah dalam mengesan kebarangkalian berlakunya MI berdasarkan analisa isyarat elektrokardiogram (ECG) dalam masa sebenar. Peningkatan segmen ST dalam isyarat ECG dijadikan penanda aras dalam menentukan isyarat ECG yang mengandungi MI. Analisa isyarat dijalankan melalui perisian MATLAB untuk mendapatkan ciri ECG dan penyisihan ST, serta pengesanan MI. Proses dalam mengenal pasti MI dimulakan dengan pengumpulan isyarat ECG yang boleh didapati secara percuma daripada pengkalan data laman sesawang Physionet, diikuti dengan pra-pemprosesan isyarat ECG untuk menurus dan membetulkan garis asas. Kemudian, pemprosesan isyarat ECG dilakukan untuk mendapatkan ciri-ciri ECG, iaitu puncak-puncak P, Q, R, S, dan T. Setelah itu, analisa Hasil Kumulatif (CUSUM) dijalankan bagi mengesan mana-mana penyisihan dalam spektrum penaikan ST dan akhir sekali, amaran dikeluarkan sekiranya terdapat tanda MI dalam isyarat ECG. Penetapan saiz tettingkap yang betul dikaji dalam penyelidikan ini dalam mencapai ketepatan dan pengkhususan yang optimum melebihi 90%. Pada umumnya saiz tettingkap yang besar digunakan untuk data yang tidak mengalami perubahan mendadak, manakala saiz tettingkap yang kecil digunakan bagi data yang mengalami perubahan mendadak. Dengan penetapan tettingkap yang tepat di samping analisa CUSUM yang berkesan, MI boleh dikesan pada peringkat awal melalui analisa isyarat ECG.

Kata kunci: Infarksi Miokardium; Elektrokardiogram; Peningkatan ST; Hasil Kumulatif; Saiz Tettingkap

INTRODUCTION

Myocardial Infarction (MI) occurs to people who are having ischemia disease, a condition where the flow of oxygenated blood to heart muscle is being interrupted (Al-Kindi & Tafreshi 2011). Myocardial infarction may lead to diastolic or systolic dysfunction and may increase the susceptibility to arrhythmias and other complications (Helwan et al. 2017). This is because of the blockage of coronary arteries due to the formation of plaques. The interruption thus decreases the efficiency of heart to pump oxygenated blood to other parts of body. MI

also can be called as heart attack. Early diagnosis for MI is important to save live, because highest die risk occurs at early stage MI (Mehri et al. 2018).

Electrocardiogram (ECG) monitoring machine can capture ECG signal for the further analysis. This device can read ECG signal and shows P, QRS, and T waves from heart signal (Shahid 2017). Probe is being used to detect electrical current in body (Mary 2017). Analysis on ECG signal is done to identify if there present any abnormalities in signal. Figure 1 shows a normal signal consisting of a waveform from ECG recording. The normal signal consists of P wave, PR interval, QRS complex, ST segment, and

T wave (Alsaedi 2017). Our point of interest is ST segment, which is the segment between the offset of S wave and the onset of T wave. The characteristics of ST segment that represents MI are the amplitude of ST segment elevation is more than 0.2 mV and this occurs in a long time period (Hwang & Levis 2014)..

FIGURE 1. The normal ECG signal

Based on the previous researches, the researchers managed to achieve high accuracy and specificity, which are up to 80% but we believed that we can achieve sensitivity and specificity more than 90%. Al-Kindi and Tafreshi (2011) in their research entitled “Real-time Detection of Myocardial Infarction by Evaluation of ST-segment In Digital ECG” has managed to achieve 85% sensitivity in detecting MI incidents with no false detection. Other researches such as Kumar et al. (2017) entitled “Automatic Diagnosis of Myocardial Infarction ECG Signals Using Sample Entropy in Flexible Analytic Wavelet Transform Framework” manages to achieve accuracy more than 90% in detecting MI. Kuchar et al. (1987) states that by using a combination of noninvasive tests after myocardial infarction, patients can be stratified according to a risk of serious arrhythmic events.

The objectives of this paper are first, to create alarm that warn users if MI has been detected in ECG signal, so that users can be aware of their own health condition. Next, we are also intend to build an algorithm based on the MATLAB programming to detect MI from the evaluation of ST segment elevation. Lastly, the objective of this research is mainly to reach sensitivity and specificity rate up to 90%.

Few steps are followed in order to detect MI. First, ECG data are collected from the Physionet website (Goldberger et al. 2000), followed by ECG signal pre-processing to remove noise and correct baseline wandering. Next, the filtered and corrected baseline wandering signal is processed to extract ECG features. Cumulative sum (CUSUM) analysis is used to detect if ST deviation occur in ECG signal, and lastly the confirmation of ECG signal that contains MI can be done. CUSUM analysis involves sequential detection procedures (Granjon 2012).

In this paper, CUSUM analysis was proposed to detect a change in ST amplitudes. The correct setting for sliding window in detecting ECG features is

investigated to achieve high sensitivity and specificity.

METHODOLOGY

ECG data collection

ECG recordings were obtained from European ST-T (EDB) Database and MIT-BIH Normal Sinus Rhythm Database. Physionet website provides a platform for this collection of data. These clinical databases were prepared by a group of researchers for a research purpose. Fifteen ECG recordings were used in this study; ten that comes from patients with myocardial infarction and five were from healthy control subjects. The analysis of MI was based on the clinical diagnoses provided by the website. The important information such as frequency sample, the number of data, the length of data, and the bit resolution were needed in the analysis. EDB database subjects have various heart problem (vessel disease, hypertension, ventricular dyskinesia, coronary artery disease, and myocardial infarction) but in our research, myocardial infarction are chosen as our interest disease. Each data was sampled at 250 samples per second with two hours duration for EDB database and 128 samples per second for MIT-BIH Normal Sinus Rhythm database. These raw data need to go through a step of processing before MI can be detected in the signal.

ECG signal pre-processing

First, raw signal undergone denoising using four level wavelet decomposition by Daubechies-4 filter. This filter consists of low pass and high pass filter. These filters worked independently in denoising the signal. Low pass filter yielded approximation coefficient vector by down sampling the signal. Second level approximation coefficient was used as it provided the least noisy, therefore details were reduced. The signal now has quarter number of samples. Similarly, the high pass filter yielded detail coefficient vector which contains the noise and high frequency components of the signal.

Next, the baseline wandering in a raw ECG signal was corrected. The raw ECG signal was first filtered with a finite impulse response (FIR) low pass filter. After that, a 200 ms median filter was used to eliminate noise of QRS complex and then passed through a 600 ms median filter to remove noise of T wave. Then, this signal was subtracted from the low pass filtered signal. The ECG signal with corrected baseline wander was obtained from the difference between the two signals.

ECG signal feature extraction

ECG analysis using MATLAB was done to extract ECG features. From this analysis, P, Q, R, S, and T peaks locations and amplitudes can be detected. Each peak matrix has the locations in column 1 and

amplitudes in column 2.

Extraction of ECG features started with detecting the R peaks and their positions in the signal. These R peaks were set as reference as they were surely the highest maxima, so we set the threshold of R peaks as 70% from the maxima peak. Then based on the reference, other peaks (P, Q, S, and T) can be extracted from the findings of maximas and minimas. First, detail coefficients of the original signal was taken via second level wavelet decomposition to detect R peaks. All R peaks were squared to get only positive peaks and the positions of the maxima in a sliding window were saved. Next, other peaks can be detected by went back and forth with reference of R peaks to detect any maxima and minima in that location.

Size of sliding window is very important parameter to get an accurate result. If the size of the window is too small, the sensitivity of the algorithm is decreased thus it may detect new changes and lead to false detection. If the size of window is too large, the algorithm does not done the analysis thoroughly, thus may miss some important information. Table 1 shows the approximate sliding window gotten from the algorithm and the actual window used in the analysis to extract ECG features. The actual window for detecting peaks were used in algorithm for signal analysis.

TABLE 1. The approximate and actual sliding windows for peak detection

Signal	Approximate window	Actual window
E0105	1.1	1.1
E0123	0.9	0.75
E0124	0.9	0.8
E0163	1.03	1.05
E0166	1.28	1.25
E0408	0.96	0.85
E0509	0.8	0.85
E0604	1.12	0.95
E0607	0.84	0.85
E0615	0.85	1

Cumulative sum (CUSUM) analysis

CUSUM analysis was done to detect MI in ECG signal. CUSUM analysis uses cumulative sum approach to detect change in a signal which is based upon the repeated use of the sequential probability ratio test (SPRT).

Before CUSUM analysis is done, ST elevation spectrum is extracted first. From S-offset and T-onset, we can measure ST segment amplitude. We consider only ST elevation case, rather than non ST elevation case because ST elevation is more specific to MI. Thus only positive amplitudes of ST segment are recorded. CUSUM analysis was done on the ST elevation spectrum to detect new and significant ST elevation changes in ECG signal. CUSUM analysis was done due to the fact that time duration for ST elevation should be prolonged enough to confirm the occurrence of MI. Hypothesis testing was done in this analysis to detect MI. Two hypothesis were set:

the null hypothesis, H_0 as the normal signal and the alternate hypothesis, H_1 as the MI signal.

For the CUSUM analysis, the values of ST segments were recorded as a sequence $ST = ST[0], \dots, ST[n]$. We assume that the ST samples are normally distributed with a mean π and a variance σ^2 . Recursive form of the CUSUM algorithm was used to detect when and if we change from H_0 to H_1 .

First, deviation value, d and threshold value, h . A threshold of more than 0.2 mV were set to indicate ST segment elevation. A parameter for minimum number of detections to be detected before raising an alarm, k was set. In algorithm, ST segments were measured to detect deviation. A minimum value for deviation was set and if deviation exceeded the minimum value, it will be recorded. The sum of this deviations were calculated, and if the sum of deviation were more than k , alarm will be raised to indicate MI. The deviations calculated were based on the algorithm from window to window, where window was shifted to right by one value.

MI detection

To detect MI, a several parameters need to be set first. The parameters are h for threshold whether to accept or reject hypothesis, k for the minimum number of detections to be detected before raising the alarm, w for window size in which ST samples will be considered, and d for the most likely change magnitude for ST elevation.

Detection threshold, h was set to 2. If the algorithm detect a ST elevation higher than detection threshold, the ST elevation were recorded as an indicator of MI. Then, sum of the deviations were calculated and if this sum exceeded minimum number of ST elevations to detect for alarm, an alarm will be raised to indicate the occurrence of MI in the signal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows an example of raw ECG signal from record e0105 which contain noises. These noises make analysis for peak detection becomes difficult, so we need to filter and denoise it. High pass filter is needed to eliminate the lower component in order to get a smooth signal.

FIGURE 2. The raw ECG signal

FIGURE 3. The filtered ECG signal

FIGURE 4. ECG signal after baseline removal

FIGURE 5. ECG signal with identified P, Q, R, S, and T peaks

FIGURE 6. An alarm that shows ECG data contain MI marker

Figure 3 shows the ECG filtered signal after pass through wavelet decomposition. The second level of Daubechies-4 filter which resamples the signal to quarter of its samples is the best for the feature extraction due to its characteristics that produce least

noise. Figure 4 shows the baseline corrected signal. ECG signal's noises that come from electromagnetic interference, muscle activity, electric and power line interference, bowel movements, and lead placement on the body lead to the baseline wander of signal. The difference between the median filtered signal and low passed filtered signal successfully produce the ECG signal with corrected baseline wander. This process is important, so that we can detect ECG peaks accurately. Figure 5 shows the ECG signal with P, Q, R, S, and T peaks. Too small window size reduces the sensitivity of the algorithm in detecting ST deviations leading to wrongly detected warning. If the window size is too big, it will lead to failure in obtaining important information regarding signal. With the corrected sliding window and baseline corrected signal, we managed to detect peaks with the accuracy up to 90%. Figure 6 shows an alarm displayed to warn the users that ECG signal contains MI. This alarm is raised after CUSUM analysis with the threshold $h=2$, the minimum deviations $k=1$, the sliding window $w=100$, and change magnitude $d=25$.

In order to evaluate the proposed MI detection algorithm, the sensitivity and specificity are formulated as in equation (1) and (2), respectively.

$$\text{Detection Rate} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{False Alarm Rate} = \frac{FP}{FP+TN} \quad (2)$$

Where TP is true positives, FP is false positives, TN is true negatives, and FN is false negatives. TP is a condition in which we predicted yes (MI is occurred), and they are proven to have MI. TN is a condition in which we predicted no (MI is not occurred), and they are proven don't have MI. FP is a case in which we predicted yes, but they don't actually have MI. lastly, FN is we predicted no, but they actually do have MI.

Detection rate, or also known as sensitivity is a rate to calculate how often it predicts yes when it's actually yes. False alarm rate calculate on how often it predicts yes when it's actually no, thus indicate the effectiveness of the algorithm in differentiate between MI signal and normal signal. Based on the research done, the proposed algorithm was managed to detect 91% of the patients with MI (sensitivity) and zero false detection (specificity).

CONCLUSION

In this research, an algorithm using MATLAB as a programming language has successfully been developed to detect ST elevation from ECG signal in a real time manner. The ECG features (P, Q, R, S, and T peaks) have been extracted through an algorithm with the modified sliding window. We managed to achieve an accuracy up to 90% in detecting peaks. In order to produce an algorithm

that can detect MI with a high sensitivity and specificity, the correct size of sliding window plays an important role. Incorrect size of sliding window will lead to an inaccurate rate of detection of MI. As a conclusion, MI can be detected from the ECG signal at an early stage by analyzing of ST segment in a real time manner.

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